

Research

Transfer learning for crash design

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Abstract

When designing the structure of a new vehicle, car manufacturers need to ensure the compliance with strict safety requirements. Aiming to support the engineers in the early phase of this process, we propose a transfer learning framework for crashworthiness. This work explores the possibility to infer knowledge on future situations by exploiting data coming from past development processes. During the early phases of automotive development, assessing the crash safety implies dealing with the challenge of low data availability. Here, the engineers have no hardware test to rely on and can access only few finite element simulations. Under these circumstances, an attractive concept to investigate is the development of a machine learning approach able to learn from the past designs and to transfer the acquired knowledge to the new ones. Transfer learning can serve to this aim. With it, one learns the basic knowledge from a source domain A, and transfers it to a target domain B, characterized by low data availability. Here, we propose a transfer learning framework and apply it to an explicatory industrial crash example. The components produced in the past constitute the source domain; the new component design is the target domain. The proposed methodology can serve as an innovative solution to support car manufacturers in the early phase of vehicle development and thus improve the performance in crashworthiness scenarios.

Keywords Crashworthiness · Early-phase design · Transfer learning · Multi-fidelity modeling · Machine learning

1 Introduction

Designing safe vehicles is an absolute necessity in the automotive industry. To ensure the safety of drivers, passengers, and other road users, automotive companies need to ensure the compliance of the vehicle with strict safety requirements. These requirements are set by e.g. the United Nations regulations or regulatory agencies such as the National Highway Traffic Safety Administration (NHTSA) in the United States [1]. One of the requirements that the engineers must comply with is vehicle crashworthiness, that refers to the ability of a vehicle to protect its occupants during a crash. Assessing vehicle crashworthiness is an expensive and complex task that recurs in different phases throughout the whole vehicle development process.

During the early development phase, engineers mainly rely on computer-aided design (CAD) software to design the car and on finite element (FE) simulations to model its performance in a crash. In this phase, the structural design of the car is iteratively checked for areas that may need improvement. Once the early phase is completed, a hardware prototype of the car is built and its crash performance is physically evaluated through destructive tests in multiple load case scenarios. The assessment continues with the final product, to ensure that it meets the required standards. Although the

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safety evaluation is continuous and iterative along the development of the vehicle, intervening during the initial phase is crucial to ensure a seamless and cost-effective process.

Defining a crashworthy design in the very early phase of the development is hence considered essential. By conducting an in-depth assessment of the car safety performance in the early phase, one can avoid the high costs associated with modifying the car prototype or, furthermore, necessitating changes in the pre-series production. This early safety assessment in a highly uncertain and ambiguous environment is, however, arduous, as the engineers need to face the challenge of low data availability. Given the influence of the VUCA (volatility, uncertainty, complexity, and ambiguity) factors, the ultimate geometrical information, material properties and characteristics of the new product are, as a matter of fact, not yet entirely available. Moreover, the assumptions and the decisions of the engineers regarding the crash performance of the vehicle are, in this phase, based on FE simulations that can be tough to perform, validate, and evaluate.

The complexity of FE simulations for crash depends on several factors: the need for replicability, the difficulty in modeling the vehicle and its parts accurately, the requirement of significant computational power, and the need to correlate the simulation results with real-world testing. In the early development phase, therefore, engineers take decisions and apply changes also based on their expertise: a new product is often considered as a broad modification of past ones.

In industry, many new products can indeed be seen as modifications or upgrades of existing ones. Modifying current products is often more cost-effective than starting from scratch, and it also allows companies to build on the brand recognition that they have already gained. This scenario, merged with the need of providing the engineers with a tool to support the early phase vehicle development, suggests to explore methods that can automatically gather information from prior designs and exploit it to guide future development processes.

In this paper, we propose a machine learning (ML) method that precisely fulfills this goal: gaining knowledge from the past and transferring it to the future. The decision to utilize ML techniques is driven by the inherent flexibility that they offer: different architectures can be chosen to operate with data of different nature. Moreover, ML approaches allow for great adaptability to complex and highly non-linear scenarios. This is in strong contrast to other techniques available in the literature, e.g. conventional statistical methods or simple regression techniques, which are unable to address the challenges posed by high dimensions and non-linear problems [2], such as those commonly encountered in crash analysis.

Nowadays, traditional ML technology exhibits a resounding success in a multitude of practical applications, e.g. email spam filtering [3, 4], image recognition [5], natural language processing [6, 7], medical diagnosis [8, 9], etc. An ideal application scenario for ML requires abundant training instances [10]. In many situations, however, like the one addressed in this work, collecting sufficient training data is often expensive, time-consuming, or even unrealistic.

One approach that intends to alleviate the demand for significant amounts of data is transfer learning (TL). As it helps to mitigate this challenge by exploiting the knowledge acquired from pre-accomplished tasks, TL becomes a promising approach in situations where only a limited amount of data is available for a specific task [11]. This method enables the efficient utilization of pre-existing models trained on one dataset, namely, the source domain, to a new dataset called target domain, thus reducing the need for large amounts of data and time-intensive model training.

To the best of the authors' knowledge, the only example in the literature that approaches the intersection of TL and crash analysis is the development of a geodesic convolutional neural networks [12]. This work, however, does not embrace the paradigm of generalizing across different vehicle models or to predict outcomes for future, untested designs. In this paper, this gap is bridged. This paper focuses on proposing a TL framework for crash analysis, exploring the transfer of knowledge between different mechanical systems, specifically moving from older to newer models. Through this work, we seek to bridge the gap between product design history and future crashworthy product development in the early design phase, characterized by low data availability.

In general, TL is inspired from human beings. We have the ability to transfer the knowledge gained from a past experience to a new one; in the same way, TL is supposed to learn and apply knowledge from the source domain to the target one, even if they are not directly related. Under the assumption, however, that the two domains are similar, TL relies on extracting the basic knowledge from the source and applying it to fulfil the required target task [13].

With TL, one can decide to either make use of a pre-trained model or to train the source model from scratch. The choice between the two options depends on multiple factors, e.g. the availability of labeled data, computational resources and the type of data to be treated. Depending on the specific situations, both techniques—using a pre-trained model or training a model from scratch—have their own advantages.

Pre-trained models are nowadays largely utilized because they can be adapted to specific tasks, allowing to capture rich representations of data and perform well on various TL applications. By providing a way to leverage large-scale pre-training on massive datasets, these models have become a key component to achieve impressive performance in various domains [14, 15]. As an example, models like Visual Geometry Group (VGG) [16], ResNet [17], Inception

[15], and EfficientNet [18] are widely used in image classification tasks; in the natural language processing (NLP) field, models like BERT (Bidirectional Encoder Representations from Transformers) [14], GPT (Generative Pre-trained Transformer) [19], and RoBERTa (Robustly Optimized BERT Pre-training Approach) [20] produce significant advances in correctly accomplishing the language processing task; models like DeepSpeech [21] and Wav2Vec (Waveform-to-Vector) [22] are trained on large-scale speech datasets to perform automatic speech recognition tasks.

When using pre-trained models in TL, the already learned parameters are typically modified to fit a related target task. The pre-training process involves training a deep neural network (NN) on a massive dataset, often using a large amount of computing resources. The advantage of using a pre-trained model is that it has already learned useful features and patterns from the source data it is trained on, which can be valuable for other tasks [5].

The cited works refer to the exceptional performance of TL applied to pre-trained models across various ML domains. As of yet, however, mechanical engineering applications of TL on pre-trained models appear to be only sparsely reported. Industrial scenarios require careful consideration of the data constraints. On the one hand, in vehicle design, the cost and time required to collect the data can be substantial, making it difficult to build robust models; on the other hand, the distributions and characteristics of industrial data are usually far from the ones on which pre-trained models are built. This domain shift could cause a significant drop in performance when directly applying pre-trained models to specific engineering tasks. Researchers have risen to these challenges by devising innovative approaches to create ML models from scratch, demonstrating the versatility, adaptability, and potential of TL in these scenarios e.g. [23, 24, 25]. Building source TL models from scratch, however, can itself be a challenging task.

To tackle this obstacle and propose successful application of TL for industrial purposes, researchers rely on different alternatives, e.g. exploiting simulation data [23, 26, 27], using large open-source databases [28, 29], or performing data augmentation [30]. Simulations provide a valuable alternative, enabling the generation of diverse and controllable synthetic data that mimics real-world scenarios. Authors in [23], for example, use TL to support designers in the initial set up of the injection molding procedure: by means of only a small amount of experimental data and a larger one of simulations, they manage to predict quality-related criteria for process parameters. In [24], the authors propose a TL approach to enhance the fault types classification of rolling bearings in different working conditions. In [31], authors contribute to the research of TL for fault diagnosis by focusing on gear transmission. Further recent applications of TL to industrial cases can be found, for instance, in [32] and [25]. In the former, the authors focus on TL for booming noise classification when only a few data are available and, in the latter, not enough labeled instances can be collected. Generally, the state-of-the-art works on TL illustrate that its effectiveness depends on two contributing factors: the quality of the source model, and the similarity between the two domains [33].

The literature shows that the source domain data can come from a different mechanical system with respect to the one on which the target data have been collected [34, 35]. In this case, dissimilarities in the data distributions and underlying features can be expected. These differences can pose challenges to the transfer of knowledge, as the pre-trained models knowledge might not be directly applicable to the target domain. If the source and target domains are too dissimilar or unrelated, it can lead to a phenomenon called negative transfer, where the model performs worse on the target domain than a model trained from scratch. Negative transfer can occur because the pre-trained model may have learned features or patterns that are irrelevant or even detrimental to the target domain [36]. Given these considerations, determining the similarity between the source and target domains is a crucial step in TL.

The authors of [37] define TL between different mechanical systems as across different machines. They divide it into three typical applications: transfer from laboratory to industry, transfer from simulation to reality, and transfer from past to future. The last one becomes of particular interest to the aim of this paper.

This work aims to investigate the feasibility of utilizing TL for crash analysis, specifically focusing on the transfer of knowledge between different mechanical systems. By addressing the challenge of converting FE simulations of crashes into a format compatible with ML methods, we propose a structured framework that delineates the steps necessary for effectively applying TL to crash data. Section 2 outlines the required stages for the utilization of TL for crash analysis. This begins with the data collection and preparation, continues with the observation of the similarity between the domains, as well with the TL implementation, and terminates with the analysis of the results. In Sect. 3, we demonstrate the applicability of this framework to a specific crash study case. Finally, we propose our conclusions in Sect. 4, we propose our conclusions in Sect. 4.

2 A transfer learning framework for crash analysis

The framework that we propose is built in accordance with the key steps required by an ML algorithm, as detailed further below. Additional steps and specific constraints have been included to make TL feasible for our area of application, i.e. the crash analysis domain. Examples for these additions are the selection of the variants or the translation of the variants' information in ML-readable data, see Fig. 1.

The framework is divided into four main parts: data collection, data preparation, TL implementation, and evaluation of the results. In the following, the individual steps are explained in detail. As a note to the reader, although the primary focus of this paper is placed on regression problems, it is worth mentioning that the proposed framework could also be adapted to solve classification cases.

2.1 Data collection

The first step of the procedure aims at evaluating whether the proposed framework is suitable for the application case at hand. It includes examining the nature of the problem and the availability of the data. Our framework is suited for scenarios in which a significant amount of data is available for older versions of the system, but only a few data points are at disposal for the current version.

To be compatible with our framework, the selected mechanical application case must feature scalar inputs and output(s), regardless of the methodology employed to collect the data, e.g. by means of hardware tests, simulations, etc. The inputs have to be selected based on the factors that are most likely to affect the performance of the system that one is interested to observe; the output(s) can be defined based on the specific performance criteria that are being evaluated. In the case of vehicle safety studies, the output may be measured, for example, in terms of the maximum chest acceleration of the dummy. The inputs, instead, could include the speed of the vehicle, the angle of impact, the type of restraint system—e.g. seatbelt, airbag—and the stiffness of the structure of the vehicle. In addition to assessing the features of the mechanical system, the first step of our framework also involves ensuring that the collected data belong to diverse geometrical configurations of the mechanical system under investigation.

As mentioned in Sect. 1, TL is here applied with the aim of collecting knowledge from the past and transferring it to the future. To achieve this, the selected mechanical system must be available in multiple configurations. Some configurations represent the past variants, required to build the source domain; an additional configuration *N*, the one of interest, is instead considered as the target domain, as shown in Fig. 2. The figure shows source and target domain data, and a representation of how the first are utilized to establish the source domain model. This is then adapted to the target domain data. An example of old and new variants of mechanical systems can be a car bonnet with

Fig. 1 Representation of the proposed TL framework. The dashed line around the correlation and augmentation steps signifies that the two steps can be discarded because of, respectively, limited availability of target data, or high availability of source domain data

Fig. 2 Similar variants of the same mechanical system are grouped to form the source and target domain. The white squares represent the scalar inputs and output. The figure also includes a qualitative representation of the source domain model and its subsequent adaptation to accommodate the target domain data

given shape and thickness, and a newly developed version of that same bonnet with a different geometry. While we assume to have abundant data available for the old variants, only a limited amount can be collected for the new one.

The knowledge obtained from the past variants in the source domain is used to improve the prediction of the mechanical response of the new variant in the target domain. For a feasible application of the TL framework, it is binding that all the input variables that have been chosen for the study are present for all the selected variants. For example, if the width of the seatbelt has been identified as an input parameter for the study, it is essential to ensure that all the selected variants feature a seatbelt. The TL implementation here designed requires identical inputs from both systems: target variants that lack variables present in the source ones cannot be accommodated.

After the identification of the two domains, the framework continues with the evaluation of the correlation between the two. As mentioned in Sect. 1, in TL, the success of the method largely depends on the similarity between source and target. It is therefore essential that the domains share common features, structure, and patterns. Evaluating the similarity between them, however, can be critical when they denote different mechanical systems. In this case, the data on the defined input variables of interest need to be collected for both mechanical systems and, subsequently, a correlation coefficient needs to be computed to estimate the level of similarity between the two.

A commonly used measure of correlation is the Pearson's coefficient [38]. However, there are other correlation coefficients that may be more appropriate depending on the types of data at hand. In general, correlation coefficients closer to 0 indicate a weaker correlation, while coefficients closer to 1 or -1 indicate strong positive or negative correlations. Although the strength of the correlation can depend on the context of the data, the specific research question, and the magnitude of the sample size, a good correlation coefficient can be considered, in this context, an indicator to proceed with the selected source and target domains. When working with real data, computing the correlation between source and target domain can be an intricate task, as the target domain can be difficult to test or simulate. Therefore, evaluating the similarity between the domains can be difficult or even impractical. In this case, an unknown level of correlation between old and new variants has to be assumed. After assessing the correlation, when applicable, the next step is to construct a design of experiments (DoE).

Creating a DoE consists of systematically varying the input factors to measure their effects on the output for each of the selected variant. The DoE should be structured in a way that allows for the most efficient testing and analysis of the results, and should be based on statistical principles for optimal accuracy [39]. The number of samples required in a DoE depends on various factors, like the number of outputs being evaluated, the chosen sampling methodology, the expected effect complexity, and the desired level of accuracy. After the DoE has been constructed, we are ready to proceed with the collection of the data.

The data collection step can be achieved in different ways depending on the type of system, the desired output, and the specific problem being investigated. Some of the common ways for data collection in mechanical systems are: using sensors, through tests and experiments, with simulation, or performing monitoring. The data collection has to be performed for both source and target domain, ensuring the compatibility between the two. Having a large amount of data for the source domain is important to ensure that the ML model can effectively learn the source patterns and later extend this knowledge to the target domain.

Given this consideration, and since ML models are known to be suitable for big amounts of data, the last step of the data collection consists in the source data augmentation. The way the data augmentation process is performed can vary according to the specific study case. In certain situations, this step can be neglected given the already high availability of collected data. Generally, the data augmentation step remains crucial to comply with a central hypothesis of TL: the

Fig. 3 The data are collected from both source and target domain. The white squares represent the scalar inputs and output; the hexagons represent the piece of information describing the variant to which the data belong

Fig. 4 The variant information can be translated to a ML-readable type: vector, matrix, point cloud, etc

high availability of data in the source domain. With the optional step of the data augmentation, the first part of the TL framework is concluded.

2.2 Data preparation

The next step of the TL framework for crash analysis consists of translating the variant information into a ML-readable type of data. Figure 3 shows the data collected through the previous steps: each data point is represented by the inputs, the outputs, and the variant information. The inputs and outputs indeed belong to the different variants that represent the source and the target domain. The data of Fig. 3 should be considered within the same framework depicted in Fig. 2, where the target domain data are not used to train a model from scratch, but are instead utilized to readapt an existing source model. The problem we need to solve is how to let the differences between the domains be accurately captured and used as inputs for the ML model. Essentially, this step focuses on finding and implementing a technique to represent the geometric variations in a way that can be effectively utilized by the ML model. In the following, we propose some solutions that could be employed to this aim.

One way to capture the difference between variants of a mechanical system is through a vector of scalar geometrical features, see Fig. 4. For example, if the source and target domains consist of different seatbelt designs, features such as the width of the seatbelt, the anchor points' position, and the tensile strength could be considered. A further technique that could be used consists of relying directly on images or CAD-based data. These can be processed and turned into ML-readable data. In this case, it is required to use 2D/3D convolutional neural networks (CNNs) [40].

In industrial cases, however, the geometrical differences between variants are sometimes too complex to be easily represented by individual features or images. In this case, we can use dimensionality reduction techniques. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) [41] or Sphere Projection (SP) [42] are two examples to reduce high-dimensional geometrical data into lower-dimensional representations to be used as inputs for the ML model. The literature offers a wide assortment of other interesting geometry classification methods, based on disparate techniques with specific characteristics, e.g. voxelization [43], multi-view [44], signed distance functions [45], point clouds [46] etc. Overall, the choice of the data representation impacts the type of inputs of the ML model. Therefore, it is crucial to select an appropriate data representation that is optimized for the specific problem at hand, as this will guide the selection of a suitable ML architecture.

The step that follows the translation of the variants information to ML-readable data is the data scaling. In TL, scaling is a critical pre-processing step that involves normalizing or standardizing the feature values of the source and target domains before feeding them into the ML model. The purpose of scaling is to ensure that the feature values have similar ranges and distributions across both domains, which helps the ML model to learn more effectively.

Typically, the source and target domain data are standardized to have zero mean and a unit standard deviation. This is achieved by subtracting the mean and dividing by the standard deviation of the data. To achieve this goal, first, we subtract the mean from each feature; then, we divide the obtained values of each feature by its standard deviation. Namely:

$$x' = \frac{x - \bar{x}}{\sigma}, \quad (1)$$

where x is the original feature vector, $\bar{x} = \text{average}(x)$ is the mean of that feature vector, and σ is its standard deviation.

The source domain data, disregarding both their shape and whether they belong to a single or more variants, are scaled as part of the same set. The target domain data are consequently scaled using the scale of the source domain. Specifically,

$$x'_s = \frac{x_s - \bar{x}_s}{\sigma_s}, \quad (2)$$

$$x'_t = \frac{x_t - \bar{x}_s}{\sigma_s}, \quad (3)$$

where x_s and x_t are respectively the original feature vectors of the source and the target domains, $\bar{x}_s = \text{average}(x_s)$ is the mean of the source feature vector, and σ_s is its standard deviation.

The choice of scaling the target domain data with respect to the range of the source data is made to ensure that the ML model can handle the unknown range of the target domain data. This reflects the assumption that the entire range of the target domain data is unknown at the beginning of the study, as these data belong to a domain for which only a limited amount of information is available.

Once having collected and scaled the data for the source and target domains, the next step of the framework requires to split them into training, validation, and testing sets. Although it might be difficult for the target domain, due to the low data availability, the three datasets need to be created by following some general guidelines.

The data should be sampled in a way that the sets are representative of the overall data distribution. The size of the sets should be carefully chosen, in order to avoid unreliable estimates of the performance or overfitting due to a too-small, respectively, testing or training set. For guidance on how to perform the data splitting, refer to [47]. For limited datasets, like in the case of the target domain, the splits can be performed multiple times, in order to provide a more robust evaluation of the model performance. With the data splitting step, the data preparation is concluded, and we move to the implementation of the TL method.

2.3 Transfer learning implementation

The TL implementation consists of two steps: in Step I, a source domain model is constructed and trained on the source data; in Step II, the same model is readapted to the few target data points, see Fig. 5. Between Step I and II, the quality of the source model needs to be tested to ensure that it is good enough to serve as a starting point for the re-adaptation phase. In this paper, we use the term architecture to refer to the structural framework of the ML model, while with hyper-parameters we indicate the arrangement of the components, e.g. layers, nodes, and connections.

Step I of the TL implementation is divided into three further parts: selection of the architecture, tuning of the hyper-parameters, and training. As already pointed out in Sect. 1, applying TL to crash analysis often poses the additional challenge to build the source model from scratch. A high level of customization is necessary when handling crash analysis data, in order for the model to be precisely tailored to the prescribed task.

Selecting the architecture of the source model depends on multiple factors, e.g. the nature of the problem, the available data from the previous steps discussed in Subsect. 2.2, computational resources, and the desired

Fig. 5 The transfer learning scheme consists of two steps: training on the source domain and readapting to the target domain

performance. To harness the power of TL theory, utilizing deep NNs like multilayer perceptron (MLP) NNs or CNNs is suggested. Once the architecture is selected, we move to the selection of the suitable hyperparameters and the training of the model.

Selecting the hyperparameters of the source model in terms of number of layers, number of neurons and learning rate is an important task. A trial-and-error procedure, as well as specific Python libraries and functions can be used to this aim. The *RandomizedSearchCV* and the *GridSearchCV* are two examples [48]. They are used to tune the hyperparameters in ML models by searching through a predefined parameter space.

The third part of Step I consists of the training procedure. After selecting the loss function, the optimizer, and the number of training epochs, the training data can be fed to the model. Its parameters can be then iteratively optimized. Before moving to Step II for the re-adaptation, the quality of the source model needs to be checked.

The performance of the source model can significantly impact the success of the re-adaptation process. In case of poor performance on its original task, the source model might not be good enough to serve as a starting point for the re-adaptation phase. The model performance can be evaluated through various metrics, such as the mean absolute error (MAE), the mean squared error (MSE), the R-squared (R^2), etc. Although MAE and MSE metrics depend on the range of values of the specific problem, in general, a low value for MAE or MSE and a high R^2 value, such as 0.7 or above, indicate good model performance. Once the source model has been established as good enough, the framework can proceed to Step II, namely the re-adaptation step.

Based on the literature, Step II can be accomplished in multiple ways [10]. The choice for the re-adaptation technique depends on the characteristics of the specific study case and is influenced by the initial model architecture coming from Step I. In this section, we propose a detailed description of four not exhaustive fine-tuning techniques that can be implemented for Step II: three for MLP and one for CNN source models. Fine-tuning is a type of re-adaptation technique that consists of updating the weights of a pre-trained model using a smaller target dataset. This procedure is known to be particularly useful in industrial situations like the one at hand, where the target domain has limited data [49].

The first three fine-tuning techniques — here for simplicity referred to as TL I, TL II, and TL III — that we propose are specific for MLP architectures, see Figs. 6, 7, 8, 9. Note that all three techniques have one thing in common: they focus on the modification of the final fully connected layers of the original source model. The authors of [50] suggest that the choice of whether or not to fine-tune the weights of the first layers of the NN depends on the size of

Fig. 6 The MLP source model obtained from Step I

Fig. 7 A schematic representation of the proposed TL I

Fig. 8 A schematic representation of the proposed TL II

Fig. 9 A schematic representation of the proposed TL III

the target dataset and the number of parameters in the first transferred layers. Specifically, if the target dataset is small and the total number of parameters of the source model is large, a re-adaptation of the first layers may result in overfitting. For this reason, we propose three techniques in which the initial layers are kept frozen.

TL I follows a procedure similar to the one adopted in [27, 51]. In TL I, the fine-tuning procedure is accomplished by keeping the whole source domain model unchanged while appending to it an additional fully connected layer. A preliminary trial-and-error procedure is performed to select the number of neurons of the new layer. As represented in Fig. 7, the newly-added layer establishes a one-to-one mapping relationship between the output of the source NN, and the quantity of interest for the target data. During the re-adaptation training process, the parameters of the source domain model remain fixed and the weights and biases of the new just-added layer are initialized and fine-tuned. TL I, with its simple implementation, results in a straightforward low-complexity methodology to treat the data of the problem at hand.

TL II is similar to the procedure explained by the authors in [50]. In TL II, the fine-tuning procedure consists of modifying the weights of the last fully connected layer of the NN, see Fig. 8. During the re-adaptation procedure, all the layers of the initial source model except the last one are frozen. The weights of the last layer are modified during the re-adaptation training process. The initial guess for the weights of the last layer is not random, but equal to the configuration of weights obtained at the end of Step I. This approach allows the final model to learn the core relationship in the first layers and apply it to the specific domain with the last layer.

In TL III, the last fully connected layer of the source model is removed and is substituted by a new architecture, that is optimized according to the target domain data by means of the *RandomizedSearchCV* function, see Fig. 9. During the re-adaptation training process the weights of the reused initial layers are frozen and only those of the newly inserted architecture are set according to the fed target data.

If the source domain model built in Step I is a CNN, it is possible to utilize the fine-tuning procedure proposed in Table 1. Regardless the original architecture of the CNN, e.g. N convolutional layers followed by M fully connected layers and an output one, multiple combinations of frozen/unfrozen (F/U) layers can be tested. In the training epochs of Step II, the unfrozen layers of the CNN are free to readapt to the limited training target dataset.

2.4 Evaluation of the results

The final step of the TL framework consists of plotting the obtained results and evaluating whether the transfer of knowledge has been successful. The performance of the TL model needs to be assessed on the testing set of the target domain, where the predictions are required. It can be described in terms of a specific user-defined performance metric, e.g. MAE, MSE, R^2 , etc. Results from TL studies are generally plotted through curves that show how the model performance changes as the number of target training instances increases. Plotting these performance curves of both the source and target models, from Step I and Step II, reveals how well the model performs in the target task without and with TL.

The TL results can be further compared with a second baseline model: a model—NN, Gaussian process regression (GPR), etc.—trained from scratch on the same limited amount of target domain instances. This comparison is important to determine if the benefits of using TL outweigh the effort required to transfer the knowledge. Training a model from scratch on the target domain may in fact require a significant amount of data and, if the inputs/outputs relationship is too complex, may lead to insufficient performance.

Table 1 Cases of frozen F and unfrozen U layers for a CNN composed of N convolutional layers and M fully connected layers

Fine-tuning mode	Conv1	...	ConvN	Fc1	...	FcM	Out
Case 1	F	F	U	F	F	F	U
Case 2	F	F	U	F	F	U	U
...	F/U	F/U	F/U	F/U	F/U	F/U	F/U

Fig. 10 Schematic representation of two crash boxes: on the left, a single-cell; on the right a three-cells one. The dimensions in x- and y- direction have been highlighted as a and b

Fig. 11 Representation of the α angle and of the two extreme left and right situations

If more combinations of training, validation, and testing sets have been generated for the target domain, the results on each specific testing set can be collected and averaged. In this way, the mean value of the performance metric across the multiple testing sets gives an estimate of the model's expected performance; the standard deviation, instead, provides a measure of the sensitivity of the model to the specific training set.

In summary, TL has knowledge from both past and current variants of the mechanical system of interest. The results of the TL study need to be collected on the target domain. These results can be compared with the outcomes of the source model and a model trained solely on the target data. The former exclusively contains the knowledge of the past variants; the latter uniquely represents the limited knowledge of the current variant.

3 Crash application

3.1 Data collection

The crash application case that we investigate focuses on FE simulations of crash box geometries, see Fig. 10, undergoing drop tower tests. A crash box is a structural component, often made of steel or aluminum, that can be found in the frontal part of a vehicle and is designed to absorb energy during a frontal collision. A drop tower test, or simulation, involves suspending a rigid barrier on top of the crash box and then releasing it to simulate a sudden impact. These tests are valuable tools as they allow engineers to gain insights into how the specific crash box design might respond under real-world conditions.

The simulations for this study are run using the R9.3.0 version of the LS-DYNA solver. Our FE model is realized meshing the crash box with Belytschko-Tsay shell elements and mesh size of 4 mm; the material of the crash box is a steel modelled through the LS-DYNA MAT24 model with elasto-plastic behaviour. The rigid barrier is instead meshed with shell elements using the MAT_RIGID LS-DYNA material model. It is set to an initial velocity of 56 km/h and its mass is set according to the crash box geometry such to obtain four folds after the crash.

With the mechanical system under investigation in place, we select the inputs and output of the study. We are interested in predicting the mean value of the force-displacement curve measured on the rigid barrier during the test. Three of the parameters that are known to influence the mean force are: the thickness of the crash box, the overlap between the rigid barrier and the crash box, and the bending angle of the barrier, α , see Fig. 11. While the thickness is a design

variable, the overlap and angle are load case parameters. Summarizing, we investigate the influence of crash box thickness, barrier overlap, and barrier bending angle on the mean impact force.

The subsequent step of the TL framework is the selection of the source and target variants: six crash boxes are selected for the study. For the sake of simplicity, we refer to these crash boxes as designs A, B, C, D, E, and F, see Fig. 12. The length along z-direction is the same for all the crash boxes, and equal to 348 mm. An artificial trigger is also introduced to ensure, when the load is applied, a progressive deformation in the axial direction. The trigger is placed in the first row of nodes by shrinking the perimeter length by 1%. The crash box geometries differ from each other in terms of three geometrical features: dimensions in x- and y- direction, respectively a and b , and the number of cells in the cross-section, one or three, see Table 2 and Fig. 10.

Out of the six crash boxes, six combinations of source and target domains are considered. Table 3 represents how the six crash box designs—A to F—are grouped to create the combinations of source and target domains. Moreover, the table contains the Pearson's correlation coefficient that is computed for each of these combinations.

Each source domain contains multiple crash box variants. Therefore, the Pearson's correlation coefficient is calculated for each single source-target crash box pair and subsequently averaged to obtain an overall measure of correlation. The resulting coefficients in Table 3 are only preliminary indicators of the source/target correlation. Averaging the correlation coefficients from each source crash box to the target one represents indeed a rudimentary approach that tries to capture the overall similarity between the two domains. This method is a convenient but simplistic representation that may not totally catch the individual correlations.

We proceed with the definition of the DoE. 100 combinations of thickness, overlap, and angle values are inspected: the thickness values vary with a Gaussian distribution between $\pm 5\%$ with respect to the nominal thickness value of the specific crash box, see Table 2; the overlap values uniformly lay in a range of 25% left and right overlap, see Fig. 11; the angle α uniformly varies between 0 and 5 degrees. The variation of the overlap recalls a simplified reproduction of a small overlap crash test, in which the overlap between the rigid barrier and the vehicle's front is of 25%; the variation of the α angle simulates instead the eventual modification of the load case. Aiming to generate a good space filling, the

Table 2 FE model parameters, with t_n being the nominal value of the thickness of the crash box and m the mass of the rigid wall impacting against the specific crash box

Crash box	a [mm]	b [mm]	t_n [mm]	# cells [-]	m [kg]
A	122.3	62.6	2.4	1	226.1
B	39.5	54.7	2.5	1	182.7
C	44.0	38.0	2.1	1	92.2
D	120.0	63.3	2.2	3	396.0
E	101.0	62.1	2.3	3	408.4
F	120.6	69.2	2.0	3	408.4

Fig. 12 Examples of different crash box designs

Table 3 The six tested combinations of source and target domain and their correlation coefficients

Source domain	Target domain	Pearson's correlation coefficient
A, B, C, D, E	F	0.71
A, B, C, D, F	E	0.68
A, B, C, E, F	D	0.60
A, B, D, E, F	C	0.40
A, C, D, E, F	B	0.59
B, C, D, E, F	A	0.47

Latin hypercube sampling technique is used to sample the input space. For each crash box design, 100 FE simulations are consequently performed.

The execution of the 100 simulations for each crash box design was facilitated by an automated tool developed in-house, which streamlines the process of running LS-DYNA simulations for varying parameters. After parametrizing the necessary settings within the simulation input files, the tool automatically conducts the simulations as defined by the DoE. Each new set of parameter values triggers the execution of a corresponding simulation. A similar automated process could be replicated using a Python script. By accessing the input files and interfacing with LS-DYNA, the Python script can efficiently manage the execution of the simulations, thereby achieving a similar level of automation.

After the simulations, the results are extracted in terms of mean crushing force. Given the mechanical simplicity of the study case, and considering the collected data to be of a sufficient amount for the next training step, no data augmentation is performed. Up to this point of the data collection process, each data point is represented by five pieces of information: as input, the crash box thickness, the barrier overlap, the barrier bending angle, and the crash box design (A, B, C, etc.), and as output the mean crushing force.

The crash box case study presented in this work is chosen for its balance between simplicity and relevance to real-world engineering challenges. This example serves as an effective proving ground for the proposed TL framework, particularly in the context of limited data availability. Although the simulations are relatively inexpensive to perform, the principal advantage of employing this case study is not to minimize computational costs, nor to directly improve the design of the crash box itself, but to demonstrate the validity of the TL methodology in a controlled setting. Utilizing a simple FE model, we ensure that the benefits of the framework can be clearly understood, without the complication of more complex geometries or design factors.

3.2 Data preparation

The next step of the procedure requires to make the data ready to be fed in the ML model by transforming the description of the crash box variant (A, B, C, etc.) into a suitable format for ML applications. Given the simple geometry of the treated component, a vector of three scalar parameters is used to describe the specific designs, representing their geometrical features. In particular, we define each crash box in terms of its dimensions in x- and y-direction — a and b of Fig. 10 —, and number of cells, Fig. 13. This geometrical features representation method is considered sufficiently detailed to ensure the accurate distinction between the six available crash box designs.

The last steps of the data preparation requires to scale the data as explained in the Subsection 2.2, and to split the data in 70%, 20%, and 10% training, validation and testing sets. Preserving the assumption of low data availability for the target domain, regardless of the combination of source and target domain, only a limited amount of randomly selected data is considered for the target.

3.3 Transfer learning implementation

The TL method is implemented in Python using the Keras library [52] and Tensorflow. In Step I, given the type of collected data, MLP NNs are built. The scalar inputs are processed through the fully connected layers and with the rectified linear unit (relu) activation function. The relu activation function introduces non-linearity into the network, allowing the model to learn complex patterns. The hyperparameters of the NNs are selected with the *RandomizedSearchCV* function,

Fig. 13 Representation of the data prepared for the TL implementation. The information of the crash box variant has been transformed in an input vector of three scalar geometric features: dimensions in x- and y- direction— a and b —, and number of cells

and the training process is performed with 300 epochs. Table 4 summarizes the hyperparameters and the quality of the trained source models.

Given the high values of the R^2 reached for the source models, we proceed with Step II, the re-adaptation step. To stay true to the assumption of low data availability for the target domain, a limited amount of target training instances is used, and the TL I fine-tuning technique is implemented. Out of the three techniques proposed in Subsect. 2.3, this technique requires the lowest amount of target data to readapt the weights of the unfrozen layers. 200 training epochs are performed in the fine-tuning step.

The re-adaptation procedure is performed for the different target domains defined in Table 3. Moreover, different sizes of target training sets are tested, in order to observe how the quantity of training instances influences the quality of the final prediction. For each defined size of target training set, the re-adaptation procedure is run 10 times. Each time, the training samples are randomly selected from the original pool. In this way, we aim to provide a more robust and unbiased evaluation of the model performance. After the TL implementation, the obtained results need to be thoroughly evaluated to determine the predictive performance of the model; we move, therefore, to the final step of the framework.

3.4 Evaluation of the results

The results of the method are obtained in terms of the R^2 evaluation metric, which depicts the quality of the predictive performance. The R^2 is computed for different sizes of the target domain, namely $N = [4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19, 20, 25]$ data points. Since the task is rerun 10 times for each target size, the results are collected in terms of average and standard deviation of the R^2 . The results coming from the TL procedure are compared to the ones obtained with a baseline method.

As suggested in Subsect. 2.4, we choose a GPR exclusively computed on the limited amount of target domain samples as baseline method. Given the limited availability of target training data, we utilize a GPR rather than a NN. The amount of target training instances is considered insufficient to train a NN that can accurately predict the desired output; a baseline method like GPR, instead, does not require a large amount of data, and can be a better option as it can still provide accurate predictions with the available data.

The kernel of the implemented GPR is a combination of three components: a constant term to capture the overall variance in the data, a Radial Basis Function kernel to account for the smooth variation, and a noise term to model the observational noise. This configuration allows the GPR to adapt to both the general trends and the finer variations in the dataset. The hyperparameters of the kernel are optimized by restarting the optimization process multiple times, which helps in avoiding local optima and ensures a better fit to the data.

The baseline method is computed over the same 10 repetitions of training sets used for TL and, even in this case, results are stored in terms of average and standard deviation of the R^2 . Finally, although suggested from the framework, predictions of the source model on the target domain are discarded. Preliminary observations display a poor performance of these predictions and, therefore, they are excluded from the study.

The obtained results are plotted in Figs. 14, 15, 16, 17. The four plots refer to the first four combinations of source and target domain of Table 3. The continuous green line represents the results obtained with TL; the dashed black line, instead, displays the quality of the GPR baseline method. In the upper part of the plots, the variation of the average R^2 from all the 10 repetitions is shown, while the lower part represents the variation of the R^2 standard deviation, which indicates the robustness of the predictive capabilities of the two methods.

The variability observed in the results of both TL and GPR across the 10 repetitions arise from the data splitting process. In each repetition, a new subset of training data is randomly selected. This is particularly impactful in situations where the volume of available data is small, as is the case here described. The limited data samples mean

Table 4 Characteristics—hyperparameters and R^2 —of the source domain models obtained at the end of Step I of the TL implementation

Source domain	# Hidden layers	# Neurons	Learning rate	R^2
A, B, C, D, E	2	4	0.026	0.99
A, B, C, D, F	2	4	0.035	0.99
A, B, C, E, F	2	4	0.077	0.99
A, B, D, E, F	3	4	0.020	0.99
A, C, D, E, F	3	3	0.011	0.97
B, C, D, E, F	2	4	0.018	0.96

Fig. 14 Results obtained for the first source/target domain combination of Table 3: R^2 averages for both the TL and GPR; R^2 standard deviation for TL

Fig. 15 Results obtained for the second source/target domain combination of Table 3: R^2 averages for both the TL and GPR; R^2 standard deviation for TL

Fig. 16 Results obtained for the third source/target domain combination of Table 3: R^2 averages for both the TL and GPR; R^2 standard deviation for TL

that each random selection of training data can significantly differ from the last, leading to variations in the trained models performance.

Fig. 14 reports the results for the first case of Table 3. The comparative analysis reveals that TL and the GPR exhibit comparable performance. This is evident in the consistency of both the R^2 averages and standard deviations. Although TL does not significantly surpass GPR as predictive framework, it still shows to be a viable approach for cases characterized by low data availability.

In the second case of Table 3, i.e. in Fig. 15, TL achieves better repeatability, i.e. lower R^2 standard deviation, and higher performance values, i.e. higher R^2 mean, compared to the baseline method. The quality of the predictions increases — and the variability decreases — as the number of available data points in the target domain increases, which aligns with the expectation that more target information makes it easier to produce accurate predictions.

Fig. 17 Results obtained for the fourth source/target domain combination of Table 3: R^2 averages for both the TL and GPR; R^2 standard deviation for TL. The GPR results for this case are not visible because out of range

In the third and fourth cases presented in Table 3, depicted by Figs. 16 and 17, TL shows a slight advantage over the GPR. This advantage is not marked by notable improvements in repeatability, as reflected by the standard deviation of the R^2 , but it becomes more apparent when considering the average R^2 at low target training sizes. Specifically, for cases where the number of data points in the training target domain is less than 10, TL tends to outperform GPR, albeit by a narrow margin. This outcome, while not groundbreaking, further supports the efficacy of TL, even within the confines of a simple industrial example.

The results for the last two cases of source/target domain of Table 3 are not reported due to their low predictive relevance. Both GPR and TL reach average R^2 values below 0.5 for each training target set size, thus indicating insufficient model performance. The poor TL performance can be justified by the lower quality of the source domain models with respect to the one of the other source/target combinations, see Table 4. While this consideration seems straightforward, this result does not relate to the correlation values of Table 3.

A lower correlation value is computed for another case, i.e. A, B, D, E, F to C in Table 3, but the TL results still outperform the baseline method. This outcome and the poor results reached in the last two cases show that the correlation metric alone is not sufficient to describe the compatibility between source and target domains.

On one hand, the observed efficacy of the TL framework in the second and third cases of Table 3 suggests that TL can be a valuable tool even when the quantitative correlation between source and target domains is not strong. This indication is particularly significant in industrial contexts, where the computation of correlation might be impractical and where data scarcity precludes a robust statistical analysis.

On the other hand, this preliminary study shows a need for a more refined approach to calculate the correlation between source and target domains, especially when the source domain contains multiple variants. The current reliance on the averaged Pearson's correlation coefficients may not capture the intricacies of multi-variant relationships. The reality of industrial practice, however, still suggests that the process might benefit from the input of engineers who can draw upon their experience to evaluate domain similarities.

4 Conclusion

This paper presents a TL framework for crash analysis, where information from past products becomes of aid to make predictions on a new one. In this initial exploration, the framework was applied to a simple crash box study case, which was intended to demonstrate the methodology and highlight the inherent challenges. While the correlation between the source and target domains, particularly when the source contains multiple variants, requires further enhancement, the overall results remain encouraging. In the simple study case presented, TL proved to be comparable or slightly better than the assessment method. These findings show the attractive potential of TL for crash applications, especially when little-to-no data is available.

Car manufacturers strive to develop vehicles that are compliant with strict safety standards. Conducting an in-depth safety evaluation during the early phase of the development is crucial to avoid superfluous high costs. However, the complexity of FE simulations and the low data availability pose significant challenges to the engineers. To overcome these challenges, an intriguing area to investigate is exploring methods that automatically gather information from prior designs to guide future development processes and support early phase vehicle development.

TL has served to this aim, as it allows to gain knowledge from a source domain and use it to improve the performance in a target domain. In the present work, employing TL in a past-to-future configuration, information from past vehicles has served as the source domain, while the limited data available for the new vehicle has been treated as the target domain. Compared to existing literature on TL, our study has proposed a complete framework that, step by step, demonstrates the applicability of this promising ML technique to crash data.

It is important to note that the focus of this TL framework is not to build a surrogate of the system, but rather to generalize the learned relationship from the source domain to the target domain. This means that the focus is on predicting a specific quantity of interest, rather than modeling the entire system. Our paper also offers multiple points of reflection at different stages of the framework. The steps to be followed in the procedure have been pointed out, and the reader is encouraged to explore new methodologies for each of them. As an example, the step of the data preparation that requires to make ML-readable the variant information offers considerable flexibility and freedom in the implementation.

The observations collected from the crash box study case lay the groundwork for future applications. The TL framework proposed here is designed with scalability in mind, enabling its application to more intricate tasks, where needed. The intention is to establish a foundational methodology that can be extended to address more complex engineering designs, where data scarcity and simulation costs are significant challenges. Therefore, although this study concentrates on a simplified example, it opens the way for applying TL to tackle more complex engineering design challenges.

In conclusion, TL can be considered a powerful tool to employ in the early phase of the development when little-to-no data is available. By focusing on predicting a specific relationship of the new system, the described approach can lead to gainful insights, that can potentially serve as a starting point for uncertainty quantification, as well as for verification and validation, robustness analysis, and feasibility studies. Ultimately, TL shows to be a valuable predictive methodology for crashworthiness, providing the engineers with a tool to support their expertise and automate early-stage development operations.

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Data availability The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, Giada Colella, upon reasonable request.

Code availability The custom code that supports the findings of this study is available at <https://zenodo.org/records/10513793>.

Declarations

Competing interests The authors declare no competing interests.

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